

Speculation on Quantum Thermodynamics and the Adiabatic Theorem

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In (1) we suggested the following form for the entropy of a quantum bound state:
 $S = \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln[WW] + \int dp a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ ((1)) where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In principle this may be extended to nonpure bound states. In (2) we showed that this definition (which follows from a Shannon's entropy with a particular choice of probability) ensures that an adiabatic change in the size of box with an infinite potential leads to no change in entropy as $\ln(1/L)$ from the first term of ((1)) cancels with $\ln(L)$ from the second for every energy level n . This seems to have some thermodynamic consequences. We revisit the particle in a box with infinite potential and also examine the quantum oscillator solution as the spring constant or mass is varied and find that it behaves in a similar way for all energy levels under an adiabatic transformation. We finally consider under what conditions such a transformation would lead to entropy changes.

Formulation of Entropy

In (1) we used: Probability = $W(x)a(p)\exp(-ipx)$ together with Shannon's entropy to find an expression for overall entropy of a bound state. We argued that probabilistic features exist at the level of the wavefunction $W(x)$ and momentum wavefunction $a(p)$ and a single probability should generate an expression for entropy. We found in (1):

$$S = -k \left\{ \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln[WW] + \int dp a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)] \right\} \quad ((1))$$

In (1) and (2) we focus on $W(x) = W_n(x)$ i.e. a pure bound state, but ((1)) may apply to any wavefunction (although this needs to be investigated further).

The entropy density has an extra term related to Probability * $\ln(\exp(-ipx))$, but this integrates to 0 as shown in (1).

Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

If one considers a particle in a box with infinite potential walls then from (3):

$$W(x)W(x) = \frac{2}{L} \sin(kn(x+L/2)) \sin(kn(x+L/2)) \quad \text{where } x \text{ is between } (-L/2, L/2) \quad ((2a))$$

$$a(p)a(p) = \frac{L}{(3.14 \hbar)} \left\{ \frac{n^3 \cdot 14}{(n^3 \cdot 14 + kL)} \right\} \left\{ \frac{n^3 \cdot 14}{(n^3 \cdot 14 + kL)} \right\} \left\{ \text{sinc}(.5(n^3 \cdot 14 - kL)) \right\} \left\{ \text{sinc}(.5(n^3 \cdot 14 - kL)) \right\} \quad ((2b))$$

Here $kn = n^3 \cdot 14 / L$

One may next compute the values of the two terms of ((1)) with $k=1$ as:

Integral dx W(x)W(x) ln[WW] = ln(2L/exo) ((3a)) Note there is no dependence on L or n.

Integral dp a(p)a(p)ln(a(p)a(p))--> limit n->infinite = ln(constant/(Lpo)) ((3b)) such that xopo=hbar

The L form of the result holds for any n. Thus for any n,

S for a particle in an infinite well does not depend on L. In general it depends on n. ((4))

As a result, an adiabatic change from L1 to L2 keeping the particle in the same n energy level leads to no entropy change. Thus:

$dE = d/dL \ b \ n^n / (L^L) \ dL = -2bn^n / (L^L) \ dL$ where b is a constant ((5))

If ((5)) should follow the thermodynamic relation: $dE = TdS - FdL$ then $dS = 0$ and

Force = $F = 2bn^n / (L^L)$ or Force L = $c_1 E$ where c_1 is constant ((6))

((6)) has the form of an ideal gas law. For an ideal gas, $E(T)$. If one calculates dE/dS then one may only vary n, the energy level because $S(n)$. This suggests that:

T proportional to $1/L$, but there should be an $f(n)$ factor which is not simple.

Thus it seems that if one adiabatically increases the size of an infinite potential box, entropy stays constant no matter what the energy level, but energy and temperature change. Energy changes as work in this case.

Ground State Harmonic Oscillator

The ground state harmonic oscillator is interesting in that:

$W(x)W(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-\sqrt{km} \ xx)$ and $a(p)a(p)$ to $\exp(- [1/\sqrt{km}] \ pp)$ ((7))

These forms are the same for a classical gas in an oscillator potential, thus for this one example there seems to be a connection between quantum and classical statistical mechanics.

Furthermore, a Gaussian implies maximum randomness. We examine the entropy to see if there are any special thermodynamical features.

For a quantum oscillator: $E_n = \hbar \sqrt{k/m} (n+.5)$ ((8))

$S_x = - \int dx \ BB \ \exp(-\sqrt{km} \ xx) \ \{ \ln(BB) - \sqrt{km} \ xx \} = - \ln(BB) + \sqrt{m/k} \int \exp(-.5kxx) \ dx$ ((9a))

$$S_p = -\int dp B_1 B_1 \exp(-1/\sqrt{k/m}) \{ \ln(B_1 B_1) - 1/\sqrt{k/m} \} = -\ln(B_1 B_1) + 2\sqrt{m/k} \langle p^2/2m \rangle \quad ((9b))$$

And $\langle .5kx^2 \rangle + \langle p^2/2m \rangle = E = \sqrt{k/m} \hbar \omega / 2$ for $n=0$ Thus

$$S = S_x + S_p = \ln(\text{constant}) + \sqrt{k/m} \sqrt{m/k} = \text{constant} \quad ((10))$$

As a result, the entropy does not depend on the parameters m or k just as it did not depend on L for the particle in a box with an infinite potential. An adiabatic transformation of the ground state oscillator by changing k leads to $dS=0$ or:

$$dE = d\text{Work} \quad ((11))$$

Higher Oscillator Energy States

In (4) the entropies S_x and S_p have been formulated for all energy level wavefunctions of the oscillator. The result is that (see equations ((12)) and ((13)) in (4))

$$S_x = \text{term not depending on } m \text{ or } k + \ln(1/\sqrt{mw}) \quad ((12a)) \quad \text{where } w = \sqrt{k/m} \text{ and}$$

$$S_p = \text{term not depending on } m \text{ or } k + \ln(\sqrt{mw}) \quad ((12b))$$

$$\text{Thus } S_x + S_p \text{ does not depend on } k \text{ or } m \quad ((13))$$

This is to be expected because the spatial wavefunctions of the oscillator for all energy levels are related to variables: $y_1 = x / [1/\sqrt{mw}]$ and $y_2 = p/\sqrt{mw}$. As shown in (4) the spatial or momentum density may be described in terms of these variables. For example for S_x one has:

$$\text{Density}(x) = \text{Function}(y_1) / (1/\sqrt{mw}) \quad \text{Using:}$$

$$\text{Entropy } x = - \int dx \text{ density}(x) \ln(\text{density}(x)) = - \int dy_1 \text{Function}(y_1) \{ \ln(\text{Function}(y_1)) + \ln(1/\sqrt{mw}) \}$$

One may note the identical approach with the particle in the box with infinite potential walls. In that case, one has:

$$\text{Density } p = \text{Function}(pL=y_2) / L \text{ so that: } \int p L \text{Function}(y_2) \ln\{ \text{Function}(y_2) / L \} = \int dy_2 \text{Function}(y_2) + \ln(L) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\text{Density } x = 1/L \text{Function}(y_1=x/L) \text{ leading to } \ln(1/L)$$

Thus for all energy levels for both the particle in a box with infinite walls and the harmonic oscillator, the recipe $S = S_x + S_p$ leads to an overall S which does not depend on either L or (k,m) . In both cases this follows from the form of the spatial and momentum wavefunctions in

terms of p or x and a factor depending on the parameters in the system (other than the energy level). In the case of the particle in a box, $k=3.14n/L$ so $kx = 3.14n (x/L)$. In the case of the oscillator the result seems to follow from the symmetry of the Hamiltonian i.e. $A_1 pp + A_2 xx$.

Ultimately the parameters disappear from $S=S_x+S_p$ if:

1. One may write $\text{density}_x(y=x f_x(\text{parameters})) * f_x(\text{parameters})$ and $\text{density}_p(y^2=p f_p(\text{parameters})) * f_p(\text{parameters})$
2. $f_x=1/f_p$ so that $\ln(f_x) = -\ln(f_p)$

The density is given by $W(x)W(x)$ or $a(p)a(p)$ and so the Hamiltonian form governs the variable transformations possible. The Fourier transform form $\exp(ipx)$ leads to p and x transforming as $f_x=1/f_p$, but the Hamiltonian determines whether parameters remain even after a variable transformation has been performed. It is fine to have parameters which may be combined with E in the Schrodinger equation as in the oscillator case, but if one has $\text{Wavefunction}(y, \text{parameters})$ then one has not been able to transform away the parameters and the above results do not seem to follow. $\int dx W(y, \text{parameters}) W(y, \text{parameters}) = 1$, but $\int dx WW \ln(WW)$ is not necessarily parameter free and the entropy might change with a parameter change unlike the particle in a box with infinite potential or harmonic oscillator.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine an adiabatic transformation (based on a parameter changing) for a particle in any pure energy state in a box with an infinite potential and in an oscillator and find that with the definition $S=S_x+S_p$ there is no change in entropy. This suggests $dE=-dW$ if one applies thermodynamics to such a scenario. We find that this result holds for the oscillator and particle in a box because one may write $\text{density}(x) = f \text{density}(y=xf)$. This leads to a $\ln(f)$ term in S_x and a $\ln(1/f)$ term in $a(p)$ where $W(x)= \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Mechanics and a Classical Gas (preprint, zenodo)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Alternate Expression for Entropy in Quantum Mechanics? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box
4. Majernick, V. and Opatmy, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relationships for a Quantum Oscillator (1999) (Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator/link/02e7e523b0ea347658000000/download